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A LOOK AT JOB SATISFACTION THROUGH OCTAPACE CULTURE: AN EMPIRICAL STUDY OF PRIVATE SCHOOL TEACHERS

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Abstract:

It has been rightly mentioned that HRD means building of three Cs-Capabilities, Commitment and Culture. Where Capability building requires developing the knowledge and skills of the people of an organization and this Capability needs to be supported by commitment which comes through desire to excel, positive attitude towards work, co-operation, involvement and concern for one's own self and society. Another vital factor of HRD is building culture. Culture is a way of life. It involves creating an awareness of what is ideal and desirable. Today most of the successful private schools in Srinagar district are using the very concept and approaches of HRD to develop their workforce for the attainment of their organizational goals along with individual satisfaction and growth. The present study aims to explore the relationship between OCTAPACE Culture and job satisfaction among school teachers working in private schools.

Key words; OCTAPACE Culture, Job-Satisfaction, HRD-Climate.

INTRODUCTION:

Human resource development may be defined as development of people by providing them the desired environment, wherein an individual grows exceptionally well by recognizing his capabilities and potential resulting in accomplishment of organizational objectives and goals. The development experiences of USA, Japan & Germany relate that capital and material resources alone do not bring about development, and ultimately it is the true development of human resources. 'Better people' not merely better technology is the surest way to a 'better society' is the most popular belief in Japan. Progressive organizations worldwide have treated their people as their most important asset and probably have therefore become what they are today. The effective management of human resource is the key strategic issue for organization to face challenges of competition. The Human Capital has become an ongoing area of investment. As a matter of fact, no organization can assemble growth, potentialities and capabilities of its manpower overnight. People with human energy and capability, such as knowledge, skills, attitude, aptitude, experience, motivation, physical and intellectual, strength, and potential for growth are not readily available. Hence every organization needs to develop its human resources over a period of time and the only choice the organization are left with it is to develop them if they cannot get them readily available from an open market (Mufeed, 2005; Russ & Preskill, 2005; Pal, 1997, Mufeed 2006 b). In this context human resource development (HRD) is the most versatile area of management where in researchers, training and development professionals, economists, and politicians, chief executives and line managers within the industrial organizations relates any management problem with overall HRD problem. Nadler (1994) stated that HRD is a planned process, and through continuous efforts by management one can improve employee competency levels and organizational performance through training, education and development programs. Therefore, the major concern of HRD is development of competency, motivational factors and culture. For any Individual to perform productively, the organization needs to set a congenial climate in an organization for their development and such climate can be provided through human resource development (HRD) which encompasses the development oriented activities of the organization through

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employee satisfaction. HRD climate reveals the perceptions of the employees regarding the developmental environment of an organization. The concept of climate with special reference to HRD context i.e. HRD Climate has been developed by Rao and Abraham (1986). HRD climate is the perception of the employees about the prevailing HRD culture in the organization. It is evident from the review of literature in area of 'HRD Climate' that it has emerged as vital factor for competitive advantage in current business scenario.

Review of literature:

HRD embraces the development oriented activities of the organization for improving the efficiency of its valuable human resource. For an individual to perform productively, the climate prevailing in the organization needs to be conducive for its development. Various research studies have been conducted to determine, analyze the factors affecting the HRD Climate and perception of employees regarding the prevailing HRD climate and very few of them have undertaken OCTAPACE Culture into an account.

In the view of Deal & Kennedy (1982) and Peter & Waterman (1982) organizational culture can influence performance and commitment among the employees in an organization and a high degree of organization performance is related to a strong culture that is a culture with well integrated and effective set of values, belief and behaviors. Also in a study conducted by M. Srimannarayana (2010), on the information collected from 726 employees working in 18 organizations in manufacturing sector in India, found that the overall HRD climate prevailing in manufacturing sector is of moderate level only. Also Category wise analysis leads to the conclusion that OCTAPACE culture has been more prevalent than HRD mechanisms and general HRD climate. Training and performance appraisal appear to be more mature practices rather than career planning, rewards and employee welfare. They added that it appeared that the organizations focus more on business rather than people. Ultimately, they suggested that the organizations must introduce fair employee welfare programs and reward systems to improve employee satisfaction and subsequently to gain advantage from the satisfied workers to increase productivity. However Rohmetra (1990) conducted a study on banking sector of J&K for determining the HRD climate and the attitudinal perception of 102 employees covering senior, middle and lower managerial levels as well as the clerical staff. Her study has shown that there exists an intimate degree of trust and that attitudinally they are well-disposed towards each other. In a study carried out by Bhardwaj and Mishra (2002) with a sample of 107 senior, middle and higher level managers of one of the India's largest multi-business companies and they reported the existence of good HRD climate in the organization whereby the managers in general showed a favorable attitude towards HRD policies and practices of the organization. They were satisfied with the developmental policies of top management as well as happy with the prevailing HRD climate in the organization. In the same context, Ishwar Dayal et.al (1996) carried out a study on HRD Climate in Indian Oil Corporation and they found that the prevailing HRD Climate was favorable for the learning of employee. Similarly Gani and Rainayee (1996) conducted a study on HRD Climate in Large Public Sector Organization in Kashmir and concluded that the HRD climate existing in the organization for employee development was picking up and it was further observed that compared to managerial personnel, workers were less genuine. A comparative study on 20 leading firms in banking industry of India conducted by Priyadarshini and Venkatapathy (2004) was completed with the help of 200 complete responses which were collected from 20 leading banks. The study highlighted that employees have a strong sense of belonging and that there is sense of equality with regard to the common facilities provided to the employees. M.Srimannarayan, (2007) also conducted another study in a local bank of Dubai and found prevalence of a good HRD climate in the organization. Dr. Srinibash Dash and Professor J. Mohapatra (2012) in their study on HRD climate in Rourkela steel plant assessed the extent of developmental climate through identifying and measuring the perceived organizational culture and its various dimensions. The findings of the study helped to identify the weaker aspects of culture in terms of values and beliefs that prevail in the organization. They suggested on the basis of these diagnoses, that management can take the opportunity to work upon the identified weaker aspects and develop better organizational culture. The preeminence of human element and urgency of creating a learning organization through development of

organizational capabilities all the times, make out a strong case for the evaluation of HRD climate in organizations. Various studies reveal that the HRD climate contributes to the organization's overall health and self-reviewing capabilities which in turn increase the capabilities of individual, dyads, team and the entire organizations. Bhardwaj, and Mishra (2002), conducted a study with a sample of 107 senior, middle and lower level managers of private sector organization which is one of India's largest multi-business companies. Thus, on the whole, the existence of good HRD climate in the organization covered under study. The managers in general showed a favorable attitude towards HRD policies and practices of the organization. They were satisfied with the developmental policies of top management as well as happy with the prevailing HRD climate in the organization. Alphonsa, (2000) surveyed HRD climate in private hospital of Hyderabad with sample of 50 supervisors from different departments participated in present study. The crux of the study highlights that the supervisors perception about the HRD climate is satisfactory and there exists reasonably, good climate with respect to top management's belief in HRD climate. According to Payne and Pugh (1976) an individual needs, satisfaction and goals influence his perception of climate, while climate in turn effects the same satisfaction, goals and behavior. Forehand and Gilmer (1964) outlines the perception of OC as being influenced by personality factors and their relationship with the satisfaction of one's needs.

HRD climate can be grouped into three broad categories as discussed earlier, viz. 1. General climate, 2. OCTAPACE culture and 3. HRD mechanisms. These elements can prove important instruments for organizational dynamics, growth and effectiveness, if implemented effectively by the top management of organization irrespective of their size, nature of ownership and control. Change brought in a systematic manner by using General Climate along with OCTAPACE Culture & introduction of HRD mechanisms would result in a strategic fit between: a) employee and the organizations and b) Organization & its business environment. The brief description of OCTAPACE Culture will be discussed hereunder as our present study is focused on it.

OCTAPACE Culture: The essence of the HRD climate can be well gauged from the amount of importance that is given to the development of OCTAPACE culture in the organization. The term has been coined by Professor T.V. Rao of IIMA. The OCTAPACE items characterized by the occurrence of openness, confrontation, trust, authenticity, pro-activity, autonomy, collaboration and experimentation are valued and promoted in the organizations. The literature available on HRD climate is an evidence of the fact that a very meager amount of research has so far been carried out especially on the critical dimensions of HRD climate. Empirical studies conducted by (Kumar and Patnaik, 2002; Rohmetra, 1998; Kumar, 1997; Mishra, Dhar and Dhar, 1999; Bhardwaj, 2002; Alphonsa, 2000; Rao and Abraham, 1999) indicate that the culture of OCTAPACE values is imbibed in the culture of the many organizations to a good or moderate degree. These values help in fostering a climate of continuous development of human resources. Eight OCTAPACE values to develop the profile of an organizational culture as discussed as under;

Openness: Krishna & Rao, (1977) surveyed the organizational and HRD climate of one of the largest engineering and manufacturing enterprises in India BHEL which shows that environment of openness follow good among middle and senior managers in the company Mangaraj, (1999) in her study of the HRD system in RSP found that employee's opportunities to express their view points are quite successful. Rohmetra, (1998) conducted study on banking sector of J & K space for determining the HRD climate and the attitudinal perceptions of 102 employees covering senior, middle and lower managerial levels and the clerical staff. The study shows that the environment is less open for employees. Alphonsa, (2000) surveyed HRD climate in private hospital of Hyderabad with sample of 50 supervisor from different departments. The crux of the study highlights, good level of openness.

Confrontation: Some studies indicate that the value of confrontation has been prompted in some organizations at a good degree. Bhardwaj and Mishra, (2002) conducted a study with a sample of 107 senior, middle level managers of private sector organization which is one of India's largest multi business companies. The existence of good climate

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for the confrontations observed among managerial personnel of the organization. Kumar and Patnaik, (2002) have conducted a study on 135 postgraduate teachers (112 male and 23 female) of JNV six from all parts of the country to find the relationship between HRD climate, job satisfactory, attitude towards work, and role efficiency. The value of confrontation responded good among teachers. Sr.Alphonsa,(2002) surveyed HRD climate in private hospitals of Hyderabad with sample of 50 supervisors from different departments. The study highlight that the supervisors perception about the HRD climate is satisfactory and there exists reasonably, good value of confrontation. Mufeed (2006) has conducted study in one of the leading hospital namely Shri- Kashmir Institute of Medical Sciences (SKIMS) about perception of medical staff towards HRD climate. The result indicates that there exists a reasonably good climate for value of confrontation.

Trust: Patel, (1999) has conducted a comparative study of 20 branches of DCCBs, using 105 employees from 10 high performing branches and 10 low performing branches were selected, found that trust recorded above average. Rohmetra, (1990) conducted study on banking sector of J & K for determining the HRD climate and the attitudinal perceptions of 102 employees covering senior, middle and lower managerial levels and the clerical staff. The study shows that there exists an intimate degree of trust and components of attitudinal perception enjoyed in the bank. Sharma and Purang, (2000) Survey of 27 middle level managers in the engineering sector, manufacturing primarily power sector equipment with a view to understand relationship between value institutionalization and HRD climate. The study shows that there exists a good degree of trust among middle level managers in organization.

Authenticity: Mufeed (2005) in his empirical study of the HRD climate in Hospitals found that the value of authenticity had been well developed and signified Cohesion and trust in employees their personal relationship. Mishra and Dhar (1999) have conducted a study on 200 middle level managers of manufacturing (Pharmaceutical) and service (Banking) companies which show that the value of authenticity was recorded average.

Proactivity: Mufeed & Gurkoo (2007) have conducted comparative study in Universities of Jammu & Kashmir with sample of 521 employees about perception of teaching & non- teaching staff towards HRD climate in universities found the value of pro-activity as unfavorable. Mishra, Dhar and Dhar, (1999) have conducted a study on 200 middle level managers of manufacturing (Pharmaceutical) and service (Banking) companies indicate good value of pro-activity in the banks. Kumar, (1997) an investigation into the extent of presence of HRD culture/climate/values in a post training selling and contribution of training towards the HRD/culture climate/values in a public sector organizations, using 150 executives. The conclusion of the study shows that the training has the potential to contribute to all the values of HRD climate especially the value of pro-activity.

Autonomy: Krishna and Rao, (1997) surveyed the organizational and HRD climate of one of the largest engineering and manufacturing enterprise in India BHEL which shows that the value of autonomy responded poorly by employees. Rainayee, (2000) in his empirical study found that value of autonomy is missing factor in the banks. Rao, Raju and Yadav, (2001) surveyed HRD practices in 12 Indian organizations covering financial services, consumer products, electronics, cement, tyers and automobiles which shows that employees perceived as favorable the value of autonomy.

Collaboration: Priyadarshini and Venkatapathy, (2004) have conducted a comparative study on 20 leading banking Industries in India. Hence, from a total of 324 responses, 200 complete responses were collected from 20 banks. The study highlight that employees have a strong feeling of belongingness and there is sense of equality with common facilities provided to the employees Mishra (2002) in their empirical study found that the HRD climate among private sector managers on the states of collaboration in their organization was perceived above average Sarathi and Rao, (1988) in their HRD experiences in BHEL found that collaboration exists good among the employees in organization under collaboration the superior and subordinate working together

Experimentation: Alphonsa, (2000) in his empirical study indicate that the employees do not encourage when they suggest new things or new ideas. Krishna and Rao, (1997) found that value of experimentation was responded favorable among middle and senior managers. Mufeed (2006) has conducted study in hospital as stated earlier found the value of experimentation has been discouraged. They never encourage potential employees by sharing of their new ideas and suggestions. Keeping in view the paramount importance of managing people at work places effectively, the present study focused on the need for promoting favorable OCTAPACE culture in organizations irrespective of their size and nature of control. Despite the fact that the field has been quite fertile for researchers, not many comprehensive studies have been conducted to examine the need for implementation OCTAPACE value system among the employees of private schools in particular. In order to fill the identified research gap, the present study has been undertaken in the education sector in Srinagar district, where hardly any such research work has even been attempted so far keeping in view of the present identified research objectives.

Objectives of the Study

In the light of the above extant literature surveys the present study is poised to meet following set of objectives:

- i. To critically review the literature available on the undertaken variable.
- ii. To study the extent of Teachers perception on HRD Process through OCTAPACE Culture.
- iii. To analyse the impact of the Teachers perception of OCTAPACE Culture on their job satisfaction.
- iv. To provide suggestions and recommendations based on the results of the present study.

Hypothesis

H0: There is a significant relationship between the OCTAPACE culture and job satisfaction among private schools teachers of Srinagar district.

H02: OCTAPACE Culture doesn't impact the job satisfaction of teachers engaged in private schools of Srinagar district.

Research Methodology

The present study has adopted convenient sampling technique. In the present study the population consists of the teachers engaged in private schools of Srinagar district. A sample of 150 teachers was randomly selected from 6 different private schools of Srinagar District. The questions relating to OCTAPACE Culture were used out of 38 item HRD Climate survey questionnaire developed by centre for HRD at XLRI, Jamshedpur for collecting the data. This is the standardized and widely used instrument for HRD Climate survey. A total of 150 questionnaires were distributed in six (6) different schools covered in Srinagar district. The total number of filled questionnaire which were received back was found to be 145 so the response rate was found to be 95% approximately. Lastly, only 140 filled in questionnaires were selected for this study after rejecting 05 questionnaires for being inadequate in terms of required inputs. In order to assess Job Satisfaction, Scale developed by C.N. Daftuar (1997) consisting of 19 items (out of which two items measure separately overall satisfaction with the organization and overall satisfaction with the work) was used for the purpose of present study.

Results and Discussion

Framework for data analysis:

Five point Likert scale was used to measure the perception of the teachers ranging from "1-5" (where 1= not at all true, 2= rarely true, 3=sometimes true, 4=mostly true, 5=almost true). The mean score of 1 indicates extremely poor and of 5 indicates exceptionally excellent/ high existence of HRD climate in the sample for the present study. In

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order to make interpretations easy the mean score were converted into percentage score by using a formula: percentage score= (mean score-1)*25. This assumes that a score of 1 represents 0%, of 2 represents 25%, of 3 represents 50 %, of 4 represents 75% and of 5 represents 100%. Thus, percentage score indicates the degree to which the particular dimension exists in the sample out of ideal 100.

The entire gamut of data collected have been analyzed by using mean score, simple percentage and standard deviation, Karl Pearson’s correlation were used to test the level of significance.

Reliability of the scales:

Alpha (Cronbach’s) reliability of the two scales used is

HRD Climate Scale (OCTAPACE Culture) = .78, Job Satisfaction = .95

This indicates a very high internal reliability, based on average inter-item correlation.

Data scoring, Data analysis and interpretations:

The item wise mean scores of OCTAPACE Culture of the total sample of the teachers are presented in the Table:1

As per the table of OCTAPACE Values, the mean score for Item No.1 (3.67), item No.3 (3.56) and Item No. 8 (3.49) were found to be higher than other items which indicates that employees in the organization, trust each other and they are not afraid to express or discuss the feelings with their subordinates, they confront their problem rather than accusing each other behind the back.

Table: 1(item wise mean score, OCTAPACE Culture)

SNO.	STATEMENT	MEAN	STAD.DEV
1	People trust each other in this organization.	3.6761	0.92234
2	Employees do not feel afraid about their expression of/or discussion of their feelings with their superiors.	3.3239	0.96769
3	Employees are not afraid to express or discuss their feelings with their subordinates.	3.5634	0.90605
4	Employees are encouraged to take initiative and do things on their own without having to wait for instructions from supervisors.	3.1268	1.04101
5	Delegation of authority to encourage juniors to develop handling higher responsibilities is quite common in this organization.	3.0845	1.07897
6	When seniors delegate authority to juniors, the juniors use it as an opportunity for development.	3.3803	0.88425
7	When seniors delegate authority to juniors, the juniors use it as an opportunity for development.	3.3803	0.88425
8	When problems arise people discuss these problems openly and try to solve them rather than keep accusing each other behind the back.	3.4930	0.89240
9	Career opportunities are pointed out to juniors by senior officers in the organization.	2.7746	1.05826
10	The organization’s future plans are made known to the managerial staff to help them develop their juniors and prepare them for future.	2.9437	1.08084
	Overall OCTAPACE CULTURE	3.2700	0.57581

Job Satisfaction : The item wise mean scores of the total sample of the teachers are presented in the Table 2. Since the questionnaire used 5 point scale, ranging from 5 strongly agree to 1 strongly disagree. Here the overall score was 3.27 which indicate that job satisfaction level of employees is just above average. Examining the scores of the individual items of the JS Scale, the researcher found that the mean scores of the items no.1 (3.76), 5(3.70), 4 (3.69) and 18(3.56) are higher than other items in the scale which indicates that the employees are highly satisfied with the availability as well as adequacy of opportunities to do different things from time to time which make use of their abilities along with this they are also contended with the stability in employment. On the whole the results showed that people are happy with the work and the organization in general.

Table 2: Daftuar’s Job Satisfaction Scale: (item wise mean score)

SNO.	STATEMENT	MEAN	S.D
1	My job provides adequate opportunities to do different things from time to time.	3.7606	0.86956
2	My job provides adequate opportunities to be “somebody” in the community.	3.4085	0.80316
3	My supervisor is quite competent in making decisions.	3.4648	0.99758
4	My Job provides for stable employment in suitable ways.	3.6901	0.97967
5	My job provides adequate opportunities to do something that makes use of my abilities.	3.7042	1.03364
6	My job provides fair Pay.	2.3662	1.09856
7	My job provides adequate opportunities for advancement on this job.	3.0423	0.93253
8	I’m happy with the working conditions.	2.9155	1.06565
9	I’m happy with the way my co-workers get along with each other.	3.3803	0.86794
10	My Job provides me a feeling of accomplishment.	3.4789	0.90805
11	I’m happy with the General management of the company.	3.2113	1.06792
12	I’m happy with my past advancements’ in this organization.	3.2817	0.92864
13	There are adequate opportunities for future growth.	2.8451	0.98049
14	Social conditions are appropriate for the job within the organization.	3.2394	0.94815
15	My work is suitably recognized in the organization.	3.3521	1.04333
16	I’m happy with the kind and amount of responsibilities assigned to me.	3.3803	0.93145
17	I’m happy with the Company’s policies.	2.9577	1.07486
18	I’m happy with my work as a whole.	3.5634	0.95218
19	I’m happy with my organization as a whole.	3.2394	1.11438
	Overall job satisfaction	3.2788	0.53984

Table3: Relationship between OCTAPACE CULTURE and Job Satisfaction:

SNO.	PEARSON CORRELATION SIG. (2-TAILED) N	OCTAPACE Culture	Job-Satisfaction
1.	OCTAPACE Culture	1	.695** .000 71
2.	Job-Satisfaction	.695** .000 71	1

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In order to check our set hypothesis karl pearsons correlation was carried out, to analyze the relationship between OCTAPACE Culture one of the Dimension of HRD Climate and Job Satisfaction. The analysis showed that there exists a positive relationship between component of HRD Climate and Job satisfaction. The correlation coefficient was 0.695 (JS*OCTAPACE Culture), this indicates that OCTAPACE Culture is a contributing/influencing factor to increase the level of job satisfaction among the private school teachers. Thus, our set hypothesis stand accepted.

TABLE: 4 Impact of OCTAPACE Culture on Job Satisfaction

Model Summary										
Model	R	R square	Adjusted R square	Std. Error of	Statistics change					
I					R square change	F Change	df1	df2	Sig. F Change	
1	.786 ^a	.618	.612	.33612	.618	111.567	1	69	.000	

a. Predictors: (Constant),OCTAPACE CULTURE

Regression analysis was performed to explain the impact of OCTAPACE CULTURE on job satisfaction i.e. the amount of association. F –Value of 111.56 which is significant at 5% level of significance proves that the regression model is valid (Table 4). However, it can be said that job satisfaction is very much influenced by the presence of OCTAPACE Culture. The results may differ according to the settings. It was found during the regression analysis that 61% of the variance in job satisfaction is explained by the HRD Climate dimension OCTAPACE Culture. Therefore the null hypothesis that OCTAPACE Culture does not impact the level of job satisfaction of the teachers engaged in private schools of Srinagar district got rejected.

Findings and Conclusion

The basic objective of this study was to evaluate the extent of OCTAPACE Culture prevailing in Private schools of Srinagar district. The findings of the present study indicate that the staff perceived OCTAPACE culture in private schools at a relatively good level. The study signifies that openness of staff with their subordinates and superiors and attitude of collaboration have contributed to keep the OCTAPACE culture still at upper level. The results of present study suggest that there is still a substantial scope for improvement of various aspects of OCTAPACE Culture in Private schools of district Srinagar. In creating favorable OCTAPACE culture management should put sincere efforts to entrench the values of confrontation, autonomy, authenticity and pro-activity in Private schools of district Srinagar. Further it was found that OCTAPACE Culture contributed in enhancing job satisfaction among the teachers working in the private schools. Based on the findings of present study it is highly recommended for the organization to provide a congenial OCTAPACE Culture so as to ensure the existence of high level of satisfaction among their employees which will return in high organizational efficiency and effectiveness.

Future Scope of Study

The present study was limited to assess the perception of teachers towards only one element of HRD climate that is OCTAPACE Culture. The present study analyzed the prevalence of OCTAPACE Culture and job satisfaction among the teachers working in private schools of Srinagar district, while such kind of study can be done in all types of organizations where the human resource is the backbone of the organization. It also can be expanded to more districts, regions, state and countries. It can also be extended to know the perceptual difference in Male and Female, higher income and lower income group, senior and junior employees and so on. Against this backdrop, the present

study recommends to extend the research study by including other districts and other organizations as well with a higher sample at state/national level, so that a wider picture of the OCTAPACE Culture can be brought to front.

Limitations of the Study

Like other studies the present study also is not free from limitations and some of them are mentioned below:

1. The present study was confined to study the only element of HRD climate.
2. The present study was confined to study the OCTAPACE Culture prevailing in the private schools of Srinagar District only.
3. The findings may not be same all over India, since the teachers' perception is likely to vary depending upon the prevalent environment.
4. The sample size was restricted to 140 teachers belonging to only 6 different Private schools of district Srinagar due to the paucity of time and adequate financial resources.

References

1. Abraham, E (1989) "A Study of Human Resource Development Practices in Indian Organisations", PhD theses, Gujarat University, Ahmedabad.
2. Barney, J. (1991). Firm resources and sustained competitive advantage. *Journal of Management*, 17: 99-120.
3. Benjamin A., Human Resource Development Climate as a Predictor of Citizenship Behaviour and Voluntary Turnover Intentions in the Banking Sector. *International Business Research*. 5(1), 110-119 (2012).
4. Chalofsky, N. (1992). A Unifying Definition for the Human Resource Development Profession. *Human Resource Development Quarterly*, 3, 175-182. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1002/hrdq.3920030208>.
5. Chandrasekar, S. (1993), "HRD: Is the Spirit There?". *HRD Newsletter*.
6. Coelho, S.J. (1993), "HRD as I See it", *HRD Newsletter*, January-June, 18.
7. Dewey, John *Democracy and Education*, The Free Press., 1-4 (1944)
8. Dr.Birajitmohanty, Ms.susmitaparija, and Mr.ghansyamsahu *International Journal of Multidisciplinary Research* Vol.2 Issue 5, May 2012, ISSN 2231 5780
9. DubeyPushkar and Surenthiran N, (2013). "Teachers Perception on HRD Climate with reference to Private Schools in Western Odisha, India". *Research Journal of Management Sciences* Vol. 2(3), 12-18, March (2013).
10. Hatcher, T. (1999). *Reorienting the Theoretical Foundations of Human Resource Development: Building a Sustainable Profession and Society*. Academy of Human Resource Development 1996 Conference Proceedings, Arlington, VA, p. 7-1.
11. Hyde, A.M., Deshpande, S. and Mishra, P.D (2008). *Aura and Ambience in Human Relations: Private Banks Scene*. *SCMS Journal of Indian Management*, Vol.12, Jan-Mar, pp.72-79.
12. Hyde, A.M., Deshpande, S. and Mishra, P.D (2008). *Aura and Ambience in Human Relations: Private Banks Scene*. *SCMS Journal of Indian Management*, Vol.12, Jan-Mar, pp.72-79.
13. Jain V K, Singhal K C and Singh V C, "HRD Climate in Indian Industry", *Productivity*, 1996, 37(4), pp. 628-639.
14. Kalburgi, M.S. (1984), *Human Resource Management*, McGraw-Hill, Toronto.
15. KaruneshSaxena and PankajTiwari (2009). *HRD Climate in Selected Public Sector Banks: An Empirical Study*. 9th Global Conference on Business & Economics ISBN: 978-0-9742114-2-7, October 16-17, 2009, Cambridge University, UK.

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16. Mahajan, C. M., (1996) "HRD Climate in Public Enterprises: A Case Study" Prashasika, Volume XXIII No. 1 January –June 1996 pp.69-76.
17. McLean, G. N., & McLean, L. D. (2001). If we can't Define HRD in one Country, how can we define it in an International Context. Human Resource Development International, 4, 313-326. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1080/13678860110059339>.
18. Mufeed S. A. (2006), "The Need for a Focus on Key Elements of HRD Climate in Hospitals – An Empirical Study", Management and Labour Studies 2006, 31: 57.
19. Mufeed, S. A., Gurkoo, F. A. (2006), Enhancing Educational Institutions Effectiveness through HRD Climate: An Empirical Assessment, Management and Change, Volume 10, Number 2 (2006).
20. Mukesh an Parashar ,vol.2 (2012),international journal of research inn commerce. IT& management.
21. Murthy, P. V.R., & Gregory, J.X. (1989), "Relevance of Japanese HRD Practices in Sundaram Clayton," In TV. Rao, K.K. Verma, A.K. Khandelwal, & E. Abraham (Eds), Alternative Approaches and Strategies of Human Resource Development," Rawat Publications, Jaipur.
22. Noorjehan, N.G. and Nayak, S.V. (2007). Human Resource Development and Teacher Education. Discovery Publishing House, New Delhi.
23. Parthasarathy (1988), "Towards Developing Strategies for Human Resource Development," Industrial Engineering Journal, 27, pp. 12-25.
24. Praveen Chougale(2013), Tenth AIMS International Conference on Management.
25. Purang, P. (2008). Dimensions of HRD Climate Enhancing Organizational Commitment In Indian Organizations. Indian Journal of Industrial Relations, Vol.43, No.4, pp. 324-333.
26. Purang, P. (2008). Dimensions of HRD Climate Enhancing Organizational Commitment in Indian Organizations. Indian Journal of Industrial Relations, Vol.43, No.4, pp. 324-333.
27. Rao, Nageshwara, B.C. (2009). Study on HRD Climate in Vijayawada Thermal Power Station, Ibrahim patnam, A.P. Gitam Journal of Management, Vol.7, No.1, pp.248-255.
28. Rao, T.V. (1999), Readings in Human Resource Development, Oxford and IBH Publishing Company Private Ltd., New Delhi.
29. Rao, T.V. (2000), Human Resource Development - Concept and Background, Human Resources Development: Experiences, Interventions and Strategies, Sage Publications, New Delhi, pp. 24-25.
30. Rao, T.V. and Abraham, S.J. (1986). Recent Experiences in HRD. Oxford & IBH Publishing Co. Pvt. Ltd. New Delhi, pp. 23-34.
31. Rodrigues, L.L.R. (2005). Industry-Institute Correlates of HRD Climate: Empirical Study based Implications. Indian Journal of Industrial Relations, Vol-41, No.2, pp. 87-99.
32. Rohmetra, N. (1998). Towards creating a learning organization-the HRD Climate Focus.Pradigm, Vol.2, No.1, pp. 56-63.
33. Sekar N., Muttiah K and Santosh B. R., HRD Climate and its Relationship to Role Motivation- A Study among Blue Collar Workers in Indian Manufacturing Companies European Journal of Social Sciences., 36(2),171-188 (2012).
34. Shakeel, Ahmead (1999), "Human Resource Development in Universities" APH Publishing Corporation, Daryaganj, New Delhi.
35. Solkhe, A. and Chaudhary, N. (2010). HRD Climate and Organizational Performance with focus on Job Satisfaction as a Correlate: Exploratory Analysis. Technical Journal of Management Studies, Vol. 5, No.1, April-September, pp.47-63.

36. Srimannarayana, M. (2008). Human Resource development climate in India. *Indian Journal of Industrial Relations*, Vol. 44, No.2, pp. 73-84.
37. Subramani, A.K. and Akbar Jan, N. (2011). Organizational Climate Changes in IT Industry. *International Journal of Commerce*, Vol.III, Issue. 28, pp.40-41.